

Dermatoglyphics pattern variations in type 1 Diabetes mellitus patients – “A Case Control Study”

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Dermatoglyphics is a scientific study that deals with the epidermal ridges and their configurations on certain body parts such as fingers, palms, and soles. In humans, during the intrauterine life (IUL) the primary palate, lip, and dermal ridges are formed during the same period, the genetic code engineered in the genome normal or abnormal is mirrored on these developing structures. Dermatoglyphics can be used as a foretelling, diagnostic, and a prognostic tool for diabetes and other genetic diseases. **Aims and objectives:** The study was aimed to analyse dermatoglyphic patterns in type 1 diabetes mellitus patients. To analyse salivary glucose level in type 1 diabetes mellitus patients, to analyse salivary glucose level in normal healthy individuals, to analyse dermatoglyphic pattern in type 1 diabetes mellitus patients, to analyse dermatoglyphic patterns in normal healthy individuals. **Materials and methods:** A case control study was carried out to compare a total of 20 volunteers which included 10 healthy individuals and 10 Type I diabetes patients. The inclusion criteria being the young adults [volunteers] age group above 18 years and the exclusion criteria includes samples below 18 years of age, with any other systemic diseases. Spitting method was employed to collect 3 ml of unstimulated saliva and Samples were subjected to glucose estimation by Glucose oxidase peroxidase method, immediately without much time relapse. The ink technique depicted by Cummins and Midlo was used to record the finger and palm prints. Quantitative characteristics studied were atd angle, ab ridge count, third finger ridge count. **Results:** A positive correlation was found between the salivary glucose levels of diabetic individuals with their dermatoglyphic patterns. **Conclusion:** Hence Dermatoglyphics can be used as a foretelling, diagnostic, and a prognostic tool for diabetes and other genetic diseases.

Keywords: Dermatoglyphics, Salivary glucose, Type I diabetes, Finger Print, GOD-POD

INTRODUCTION:

Dermatoglyphics is a scientific study that deals with the epidermal ridges and their configurations on certain body parts such as volar aspect, fingers, palms, and soles. In humans, during the intrauterine life (IUL) the primary palate, lip, and dermal ridges are formed during the same period, the genetic code engineered in the genome normal or abnormal is mirrored on these developing structures.^[1] All configurations are laid down permanently from the 3 month of the intra-uterine life and they remain unchanged throughout the life. A positive association of the dermatoglyphic features with diabetes have been well documented in recent years.

Type 1 diabetes is characterized by autoimmune destruction of insulin-producing β cells in the

pancreas by CD4+ and CD8+ T cells and macrophages infiltrating the islets. Type 1 diabetes is a complex disease involving a combination of factors, such as genetic susceptibility, immunologic dysregulation and exposure to environmental triggers. Individuals with Type 1 diabetes mellitus require life-long insulin replacement. Type 1 (insulin- dependent) diabetes is an autoimmune disease which predominantly occurs in genetically susceptible individuals.

Dermatoglyphics are genetically determined and remain stable throughout the postnatal life, independent of age and postnatal environmental factors. They develop during the second to fourth months of fetal growth and may be modified by genetic disorders such as chromosomal aberrations or environmental factors during fetal life.^[2] This study

was taken forward to analyse dermatoglyphic patterns in type 1 diabetes mellitus patients and to correlate between salivary glucose levels.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This is a case control study. This study was carried out on total 20 volunteers which included 10 healthy individuals and 10 Type I diabetes patients. The inclusion criteria being the young adults [volunteers] age group above 18 years and the exclusion criteria includes samples below 18 years of age, with any other

systemic diseases. The study design, objectives, and methodology were explained to the selected volunteers and formal consent was acquired.

Saliva collection: spitting method was employed to collect 3 ml of unstimulated saliva. Saliva was centrifuged for 15 min at 3000rpm, following supernatant will be stored at -20 degree Celsius. Samples were subjected to glucose estimation by Glucose oxidase peroxidase method, immediately without much time relapse.

Figure 1: (A) Saliva collection (B)Glucose oxidase- peroxidase test (GOD-POD)

Fingerprint collection: the ink technique depicted by Cummins and Midlo was used to record the finger and palm prints. The hands of volunteers incorporated in the study was washed with a cleanser and water to eliminate earth and oil from the furrowed skin and blot dried to improve the nature of prints. Two A4-sized white bond sheets was used for finger and palm printing per individual (one for the left hand and the other for the right) Quantitative parameters were determined. Quantitative characteristics studied were Atd angle, ab ridge count, third finger ridge count.

Figure 2: Fingerprint collection

Figure 3: Quantitative parameters (A) ATD Angle (B) A-B ridge count (C) Third finger ridge count

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

The data will be entered in Microsoft Excel and will be analyzed statistically using the SPSS software, version 26; SPSS Inc., (Chicago, IL, USA). The normality of the data will be assessed prior to analysis using the Shapiro-Wilk's test/Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Chi square test will be carried out to determine the difference between the groups. All statistical tests will be performed at a significance level of 5% ($p < 0.05$).

RESULTS:

A positive correlation was found between the salivary glucose levels of diabetic individuals with their dermatoglyphic patterns. Mean saliva glucose level

was found to be slightly increased in cases but the difference between the saliva glucose value in cases and control was not statistically significant ($p=0.003$). The mean TRFC in was found to be increased in controls, the difference between TRFC in case and control was statistically significant in left hand ($p=0.03$). The mean ATD angle was found to be increased in cases, the difference between the ATD angle in case and control was statistically significant in both right hand ($p=0.02$) and left hand ($p=0.04$). The mean A-B ridge count was found to be increased in control but the difference between A-B ridge count in cases and controls was not statistically significant.

Table 1: saliva glucose level

S.No	Control (mg/dl) in saliva	Cases (mg/dl) in saliva
1	7.35	10.58
2	7.42	8.71
3	7.91	8.92
4	8.47	8.95
5	8.33	11.50
6	4.16	9.28
7	4.16	9.47
8	8.33	11.28
9	8.33	9.63
10	4.16	10.53
11	Mean – 6.86	Mean - 9.89
12	S.D – 1.90	S.D - 1.01
P value		0.003

Table 2: 3rd ridge finger count- Right and Left

Parameter	Group	Mean	S.D	p value
3rd Ridge Finger Count-	Control	14.75	1.01	0.29
	Case	13.0	1.25	
3rd Ridge Finger Count -left	Control	14.7	0.92	0.03*
	Case	12.85	0.58	

Table 3: ATD angle- Right and Left

Parameter	Group	Mean	S.D	p value
ATD Angle right	Control	38.7	3.09	0.02*
	Case	53.3	4.55	
ATD Angle left	Control	39.6	2.76	0.04*
	Case	54.4	3.63	

Table 4: A-B Ridge count- Right and Left

Parameter	Group	Mean	S.D	p value
A-B Ridge Count-right	Control	37.9	1.97	0.12
	Case	33.35	1.06	
A-B Ridge Count -left	Control	39.50	1.70	0.08
	Case	35.2	0.98	

DISCUSSION:

Ubiquitous interest in the study of epidermal ridges increased only in the last several decades when it became ostensible that various patients with chromosomal abnormalities had unusual ridge configurations.^[3] Specifically, these ridge patterns make decent material for genetic studies because, unlike stature and body weight, they are not prejudiced by age or postnatal environmental factors and have the advantage of remaining unalterable throughout the life and therefore can be compared among individuals of different ages, especially in the diagnosis aberrations of genetic origin.^[4]

The results of the present study indicate that Type I diabetic patients show characteristic features of quantitative dermatoglyphic markers which differ from the normal healthy individuals. In particular, Type I patients displayed a lower Third ridge finger count (p=0.29, p=0.30), increased ATD angle (p=0.02, p=0.04), lower A-B ridge count (p=0.12, p=0.08) than controls.

The publication from Germany in 1993, An entire typing of dermatoglyphics was performed and analysed in a distinct population of unrelated German Type 1 diabetic subjects and the data compared to non-diabetic controls of the same geographic region. Findings indicate that Type 1 diabetic patients show characteristic features of qualitative and quantitative dermatoglyphic markers which differ from the normal

population. In particular, Type 1 diabetic patients displayed a lower a-b ridge count (p < 0.001) and a higher transversality of the main lines (p < 0.001) compared with controls. In addition, diabetic individuals showed a higher frequency of palmar axial tr and r" triradii (p < 0.001) and a lower frequency of patterns in the fourth interdigital and thenar area (p < 0.001) than controls.^[5]

In addition, several other publications, one from India with 300 diabetic patients, one from Germany with 192 diabetic patients, and one from Austria with 249 diabetic patients exist, however, no clear differentiation was made between Type 1 and Type 2 diabetic patients within these studies.^[6,7,8]

Provided that Type 1 and Type 2 diabetes trace back to different genetic backgrounds, a mixture of both diseases might conceal rather than disclose any significant associations with dermatoglyphics.^[9] Knussmann observed, corresponding to our study, a small frequency of patterns on the thenar and a lower a-b ridge count in diabetic subjects compared with controls.^[10]

CONCLUSION:

Our study concluded that Type I diabetic patients show characteristic dermatoglyphic features, i.e., ATD angle was increased, decreased third finger ridge count in the left hand, no significant variations in a-b ridge count. A positive correlation was found between the salivary

glucose levels of diabetic individuals with their dermatoglyphic patterns. In addition, genetic illnesses such as Down's syndrome, Turner's syndrome, Klinefelter's syndrome, and others can be detected by characteristic patterns of dermatoglyphics.^[11] Salivary estimation of glucose levels is a standard for the estimation of glucose. Therefore, Dermatoglyphics can be used as a foretelling, diagnostic, and a prognostic tool for diabetes and other genetic diseases.

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